

OVERCOMING DISTANCE: EXPLORING THE MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS OF TEACHERS IN FAR-FLUNG SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

The education system thrives on the dedication and passion of its teachers. However, for those educators assigned to far-flung schools, maintaining motivation can be a constant struggle. This study aimed to determine the motivational factors of teachers assigned in far-flung schools in the Districts of Jiabong, Motiong, Wright I, Wright II, and San Jose de Buan, Schools Division of Samar for School Year 2023-2024. This research utilized the quantitative-descriptive research design, with comparative and correlation analysis, to determine the motivational factors of teachers assigned in far-flung schools of elementary comprising the Schools Division of Samar. In the main data gathering tool, the researcher utilized the questionnaire checklist. The findings of the study affirmed that in looking into the relationship between the teachers' profile variables and their motivational factors, it was found significant in terms of civil status (weak correlation), number of years in teaching (moderate correlation), and attitude toward teaching (moderate correlation). While the remaining variables (age, sex, gross monthly family income, highest educational attainment, relevant in-service training, and performance rating) showed very weak associations with motivation, their correlations were determined to be not statistically significant. Moreover, this paper highlights the problems these teachers face: lack of communication infrastructure such as cellphone signals, internet, and transportation; delays in receiving real-time updates and transmitting the needed data; lack of resources necessary for effective teaching; and absence of electricity. These factors contribute significantly to teacher unpreparedness and struggles when handling classes in far-flung areas.

Keywords: *Motivational factors, Far-flung schools, Existence needs, Relatedness needs, Growth needs*

INTRODUCTION

Education is the cornerstone of societal progress, and teachers are the architects. Their dedication shapes young minds, building the future. However, in remote Philippine schools, a persistent lack of resources hinders teachers' ability to deliver quality education. These challenges, faced by educators in far-flung areas, can significantly impact their motivation (Ucag et al., 2024).

Motivation is the internal drive that compels us to set goals, overcome challenges, and achieve something meaningful (Abbas et al., 2023). It fuels our effort and propels us towards what we value. Without it, direction and purpose become elusive. Conversely, high motivation combined with hard work unlocks our potential for greater achievements. This is particularly true in education, where a teacher's enthusiasm directly impacts student learning and overall system performance. Therefore, fostering a positive and motivating work environment becomes a critical objective for school management (Rasheed et al., 2016).

Understanding teachers' motivations is crucial for school management in fostering a positive work environment. Cultural backgrounds play a significant role in shaping these motivations, influencing how teachers view their work and interact with students (Zulueta, 2011). By recognizing these diverse motivational drivers and needs, school managers can develop strategies that empower teachers and encourage them to excel (Robbins & De Cenzo, 2012).

Beyond understanding teachers' motivations, school leaders can further enhance teacher performance by considering the role of goals and incentives. Setting clear, achievable goals aligned with teachers' needs can be a powerful motivator, leading to increased effort and improved student outcomes (Robbins & De Cenzo, 2012). Similarly, factors like salary, work conditions, and recognition can significantly impact teacher motivation and retention (Musa, 2014).

However, fostering teacher motivation remains a critical challenge in education, impacting a school's ability to achieve its goals. While a wealth of research exists on motivation's positive influence on performance (Futalan, 2013; Castor, 2017), bridging the gap between theory and sustained improvement for teachers can be difficult.

Additionally, according to Courus (2014), society today laments over the fast-disappearing bread of teachers with missionary spirit; teachers whose professionalism has come to be seen as an integral part of their character; and teachers who are deeply committed to making a difference in the lives of their people. These kinds of teachers, associated with glistening qualities have definitely changed.

Moreover, according to Ahmed (2011) educational institutions consider human

resources as their most vital asset and they consider them as a route toward success. The motivation of teachers, therefore, is very important as it affects job performance. The vital role which teachers play in the educative process cannot be overemphasized. The teacher is the single most important factor in education. Her or his far-reaching influence as an agent of constructive change in society is beyond question. Through the years, however, teachers still complain about their status, pay, and welfare with serious consequences on the quality of education. Pupils' learning depends upon effective teaching; hence, determining the factors that help in the enhancement of teachers' motivation is of prime importance to propel them to peak performance.

It cannot be denied that one-third of the teacher's life each day is spent in their work in school. Thus, he needs to be motivated to be satisfied with his job. According to Robbins and De Cenzo (2012), when someone is motivated, they try hard which will likely lead to favorable job performance. Motivation is vital as it makes teachers positive in their job. Creating a drive in them and helping them acquire the target will give them a feeling of success. This is one of the most important factors affecting human behavior. It is the attribute that moves a person to do or not to do.

With that, in this ever-changing world, there is a need for motivated teachers so that they can survive in the educational system and they can also give help in the development of the system. The researcher, therefore, being a teacher, herself is challenged to delve further into the factors aside from salaries that will enhance teachers' motivation in the performance of their job.

The Districts of Jiabong, Motiong, Wright I, Wright II, and San Jose de Buan are characterized by their remote and geographically isolated locations. Teachers working in these far-flung schools face numerous challenges, including limited access to resources, insufficient infrastructure, cultural differences, and long distances to commute. These circumstances create a distinct educational context that may influence the motivational factors experienced by teachers in the said districts.

Furthermore, according to district data from the 2021-2022 period, the consolidated Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF) indicated that 73 percent of the teaching staff achieved an "Outstanding" performance rating. However, this figure fell 2 percent short of the national target. Interestingly, when examining the Schools Division of Samar data, it became apparent that nearly 65 percent of educators stationed in the remote schools of Jiabong, Motiong, Wright I, Wright II, and San Jose de Buan expressed a strong desire to transfer to schools in more accessible lowland areas. The underlying cause of this desire for relocation was found to be rooted in their challenging experiences at their current remote postings.

While previous research has extensively investigated teacher motivation, there remains a research gap in understanding the specific motivational dynamics of teachers assigned to far-flung schools in Jiabong, Motiong, Wright I, Wright II, and San Jose de Buan. Most existing studies have focused on urban or more accessible rural areas, where teachers may encounter different challenges and have access to greater

resources and support systems. Thus, there is a need to delve into the motivational factors that are unique to teachers in Jiabong, Motionong, Wright I, Wright II, and San Jose de Buan far-flung schools.

The researcher took an interest in undertaking this study to find the answer to why after all these years, with so many reform programs embarked on in the field, Philippine education is still in crisis. People who are motivated and satisfied with their jobs tend to become dedicated and productive workers. The responsibility of carrying out the plans and achieving the desired goals of quality education lies with the teachers who teach effectively. A teacher who has so much interest, enthusiasm, and satisfaction with his work becomes contributive to the attainment of the goals of the school system.

Addressing this research gap is crucial for several reasons. Firstly, identifying the motivational factors of teachers in far-flung schools can help educational policymakers and administrators design targeted interventions to support and enhance teacher motivation. Understanding the specific challenges faced by these teachers, appropriate strategies can be developed to address their needs and create a conducive work environment. Secondly, studying the motivational factors in Jiabong, Motionong, Wright I, Wright II, and San Jose de Buan's context can provide valuable insights into the dynamics of teacher motivation in remote and marginalized areas, contributing to the broader field of educational research.

Research Questions

The present study determined the motivational factors of teachers assigned in far-flung schools in the Districts of Jiabong, Motionong, Wright I, Wright II, and San Jose de Buan, Schools Division of Samar for School Year 2023-2024. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of the following variates:
 - 1.1 age and sex;
 - 1.2 civil status;
 - 1.3 gross monthly family income;
 - 1.4 highest educational attainment;
 - 1.5 number of years in teaching;
 - 1.6 number of relevant In-Service Trainings (INSET);
 - 1.7 latest performance rating based on IPCRF; and
 - 1.8 attitude toward teaching?

2. What are the different motivational factors of teachers assigned in far-flung schools in the Districts of Jiabong, Motionong, Wright I, Wright II, and San Jose de Buan based on the following:
 - 2.1 existence needs;
 - 2.2 relatedness needs; and
 - 2.3 growth needs?

3. Is there a significant relationship between the profile variates of the teachers and their motivational factors?
4. What are the problems encountered by the teachers assigned in far-flung areas in the Districts of Jiabong, Motiong, Wright I, Wright II, and San Jose de Buan?
5. What intervention can be crafted based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This research employs a quantitative-descriptive design with comparative and correlational analysis to delve into the motivational factors of elementary school teachers assigned to far-flung areas within the Samar Schools Division.

Data were collected through a researcher-designed questionnaire, adapted from a validated tool by Comighud (2020), to ensure its relevance to the Philippine context. Unlike traditional sampling methods, all teachers in these schools across five districts (Jiabong, Motiong, San Jose de Buan, Wright I, and Wright II) will be invited to participate, utilizing a universal sampling approach for a more complete picture.

Analysis involves descriptive statistics like frequency counts, percentages, means, and standard deviations to summarize teacher profiles and questionnaire responses on motivational factors. Inferential statistics like correlation and regression analysis then explore the relationships between these motivational factors and other relevant variables, pinpointing which ones hold the strongest influence.

Ethical considerations are paramount. Teachers participate only after providing informed consent, guaranteeing their understanding of the study and how their data were used. Confidentiality was strictly maintained, with no names or identifying information linked to their responses.

Additionally, pilot testing the questionnaire with a smaller group beforehand further enhances the study's robustness. Given the remote locations of the schools, creative data collection strategies like online surveys or phone interviews were necessary and were employed. The researchers also prioritize data trustworthiness through techniques like triangulation and member checking.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following were the salient findings of the study:

1. The majority of teachers are young (27-31 years old) and female. This suggests a youthful and predominantly female teaching force in the sample.
2. Most teachers are single. This could be correlated with the young age or influenced by the demands of the profession.

3. Teachers are concentrated in middle-income brackets. A substantial portion fall in lower-income brackets. This highlights that while many teachers may have a comfortable lifestyle, they might not be in the highest earning tiers.
4. There was a split between relatively newer teachers (<10 years' experience) and those with longer tenure. Notably, teachers are absent with 16-20 years of experience.
5. District and school-level in-service training is most common. National and regional training is reported as less frequent.
6. Most teachers have "Very Satisfactory" performance ratings, with a sizable portion rated "Satisfactory". There's room for more to achieve the highest "Outstanding" rating.
7. Teachers have a generally positive attitude toward teaching. They seem to enjoy the process of teaching itself.
8. Teachers are highly motivated by factors like safety, job security, strong family relationships, and salary. They place less emphasis on social standing.
9. A positive school climate, strong relationships with peers/superiors, and a sense of belonging are key motivators. External praise is less important, but respect and recognition are valued.
10. There was a strong desire for professional development opportunities (seminars, training, graduate degrees) and career advancement linked to fair performance ratings and increased pay.
11. Civil status, years of teaching experience, and attitude towards teaching show correlations with teacher motivation levels.
12. Age, sex, income, education level, formal training, and performance ratings didn't have strong associations with motivation.
13. Teachers report significant challenges with communication, receiving real-time updates, resources, and electricity.
14. Remember this is a sample of teachers in a specific region (Region VIII, Samar). Results may not be fully generalizable.
15. Consider other motivational theories (like achievement or belonging) that might provide further insight. Explore correlations between motivation and teacher performance/retention.

teachers in potentially isolated or less developed areas. Feeling physically and financially secure is likely a major prerequisite for them. Strong family relationships and a contented life rank highly, suggesting that intrinsic motivators are powerful for these teachers. Salary, while important, isn't the sole driving force. The low ranking of social standing indicates that teachers in these locations may place less emphasis on external recognition or prestige derived purely from their profession. This framework focuses on basic and safety needs. Other motivational theories (like achievement or belonging) might also be relevant in other contexts. The words "safe," "convenient," etc., It might mean different things to different teachers. It might be interesting to cross-tabulate this with other data you have.

Motivational Factors of Teachers Assigned in Far-Flung Schools along Related Needs

Like the previous table, the Grand Weighted Mean of 4.35 indicates high motivation among teachers in far-flung schools.

Table 2

Motivational Factors of Teachers Assigned in Far-Flung Schools along Related Needs

Indicator	WM	I
1. Organizational Climate	4.78	EM
2. Relationship with Peers	4.80	EM
3. Relationship with Superior	4.80	EM
4. Working Condition (presence of camaraderie)	4.71	EM
5. Policy and Administration of the School	4.55	EM
6. Recognition of One's Work	4.63	EM
7. Leadership Responsibilities	4.12	HM
8. Public acknowledgment for better accomplishment	4.23	HM
9. Praise from other people	3.08	MM
10. Respect from other people	4.78	EM
11. Organizational Support	4.71	EM
12. Social acceptance and belongingness	3.69	HM
13. Trust and confidence in the workplace	4.47	HM
14. Sympathetic kind of supervision	4.34	HM
15. Happy Workplace	4.71	EM
16. Work itself	3.42	MM
17. High self-esteem	4.07	HM
Grand Weighted Mean	4.35	
Interpretation	Highly Motivated	
Legend:	4.50-5.00	Extremely Motivated (EM)

3.50-4.49	Highly Motivated	(HM)
2.50-3.49	Moderately Motivated	(MM)
1.50-2.49	Slightly Motivated	(SM)
1.00-1.49	Not Motivated	(NM)
	Weighted Mean	(WM)
	Interpretation	(I)

The highest weighted means are clustered in areas related to: positive organizational climate (4.78), strong relationships with peers and superiors (4.80, 4.80), supportive working conditions (4.71, 4.71), and a happy workplace (4.71). While not the absolute top motivators, factors like recognition, organizational support, and respect (all above 4.5) are still very important to these teachers. The lowest weighted means, although still in the "Moderately" or "Highly" Motivated categories, are: praise from other people (3.08) and work itself (3.42).

Teachers in far-flung schools seem highly motivated by a positive school climate, strong interpersonal connections, and a sense of belonging. This may compensate for some of the potential isolation or challenges unique to their location. While external praise is less important, teachers still value recognition of their work and want to feel respected. The lower ranking of "work itself" is curious. This could suggest that some tasks may feel routine. Alternatively, it may underscore those other aspects of the job (environment, relationships) currently act as more powerful drivers of motivation. This table emphasizes social belonging, esteem, and a positive working environment. These factors align well with the challenges a teacher might face in a more remote school setting.

Motivational Factors of Teachers Assigned in Far-Flung Schools along Growth Needs

The Grand Weighted Mean of 4.18 reinforces the pattern of high motivation seen in the previous tables for teachers in far-flung schools. The highest weighted means highlight a strong desire for opportunities related to career development and advancement: seminars, workshops, and training (4.79), career-path promotion (4.81), graduate degree opportunities (4.77), and increase in pay with promotion (4.65). Factors like a fair performance rating system and teaching as a life goal are still within the "Highly Motivated" range, demonstrating their importance, but have slightly lower means.

The factors of incentives for professional growth, scholarship grants, and the competitive nature of teaching fall within the "Moderately Motivated" range. Teachers in far-flung schools seem highly driven to advance their skills and qualifications.

Access to professional development might be seen as key to opening up greater opportunities within or outside their current setting. The desire for fair performance ratings and alignment of promotion with better pay suggests teachers want their hard work acknowledged and rewarded, which is a reasonable expectation. The slightly lower

rankings on the competitive aspect of teaching, or teaching being a sole life goal, might be a reflection of the unique context of their work. Focus on advancement could signify a desire to move beyond their current circumstances.

Table 3

Motivational Factors of Teachers Assigned in Far-Flung Schools along Growth Needs

Indicator	WM	I
1. Opportunity to attend seminars, workshops, and other form of training.	4.79	EM
2. Study leave benefits.	4.04	HM
3. Graduate degree obtained.	4.77	EM
4. Incentives for professional growth.	3.12	MM
5. Scholarship grants.	3.16	MM
6. Career-path promotion.	4.81	EM
7. Increase in pay with the promotion in position.	4.65	EM
8. Fair performance rating.	4.43	HM
9. Challenging and the competitive nature of teaching	3.72	HM
10. Teaching as a goal in life.	4.34	HM
Grand Weighted Mean	4.18	
Interpretation	Highly Motivated	

Legend:	4.50-5.00	Extremely Motivated	(EM)
	3.50-4.49	Highly Motivated	(HM)
	2.50-3.49	Moderately Motivated	(MM)
	1.50-2.49	Slightly Motivated	(SM)
	1.00-1.49	Not Motivated	(NM)
		Weighted Mean	(WM)
		Interpretation	(I)

It was important to consider how career growth opportunities for teachers in remote areas might look different or might have additional barriers compared to more central locations. It would be interesting to cross-tabulate this data with years of teaching experience.

Problems Encountered by the Teachers Assigned in Far-Flung Schools

The Grand Weighted Mean of 4.07 indicates that the listed problems are generally experienced to a significant degree by teachers in far-flung schools. The problems with

the highest weighted means fall into two main categories: “Lack of communication infrastructure such as cellphone signals, internet, and transportation” (4.77) and “Delays from receiving real-time updates and transmitting the needed data” (4.77). Other problems are still concerning but might be less pervasive.

Table 4

Problems Encountered by the Teachers Assigned in Far-Flung Schools

Problem	WM	I
1. Lack of resources necessary for effective teaching.	4.65	HF
2. Absence of electricity.	4.10	HF
3. Absence of potable water.	3.71	HF
4. Inaccessible roads.	3.72	HF
5. Lack of communication infrastructure such as cellphone signals, internet, and transportation.	4.77	EF
6. Delays from receiving real-time updates and transmitting the needed data.	4.77	EF
7. Very far from family.	3.40	MF
8. High incidence of insurgency.	3.62	HF
9. Security risk	3.91	MF
10. Others, please specify _____		
Grand Weighted Mean	4.07	
Interpretation	Highly Felt	

Legend:	4.50-5.00	Extremely Felt	(EF)
	3.50-4.49	Highly Felt	(HF)
	2.50-3.49	Moderately Felt	(MF)
	1.50-2.49	Slightly Felt	(SF)
	1.00-1.49	Not Felt	(NF)
		Weighted Mean	(WM)
		Interpretation	(I)

Teachers seem to struggle with communication, receiving real-time updates, resources, and electricity. It was worth considering if these problems are uniquely acute in far-flung schools compared to more central schools. Resource limitations and potential variations in student populations could be relevant. It might be interesting to see if there's any correlation between these student-related problems and the teacher motivation factors you analyzed previously.

Conclusions

From the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The data points to a young, predominantly female teaching force facing limitations in

salary. This could suggest that the teaching profession in Samar might need to offer more competitive salaries and benefits to attract and retain more experienced educators. The lack of mid-career teachers (16-20 years of experience) could be a red flag for potential retention issues.

2. While some teachers are driven primarily by basic needs like safety and security, social factors like a positive work environment and respect are also crucial. Understanding these motivations will help design better systems for recognition and support. The lack of a strong correlation between income and motivation hints that non-financial factors could be more important for this group.
3. Teachers express a strong desire for professional development and advancement. This suggests a workforce that wants to improve. Providing these opportunities is not only good for teachers, but it is also likely to benefit student outcomes. School or district leaders should prioritize making training and career pathways accessible, especially in a far-flung context where teachers may already face isolation.
4. Explore why teachers might leave after a certain number of years or why those in the 16–20-year range are less common.
5. Research what salaries and benefit packages would be necessary to attract experienced teachers to the region.
6. Design professional development around teachers expressed needs and the specific difficulties students are experiencing.
7. Compare challenges in far-flung schools to those in more central locations in Samar or the Philippines as a whole. This could show whether problems are unique to or simply more intense in remote areas.

Recommendations

Anchored on the conclusions drawn from the findings, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Conduct exit interviews or surveys with teachers who leave the profession after 5-10 years and especially those in the absent 16–20-year range.
2. Understand the reasons for leaving (pay, working conditions, family, career change, etc.). This will help pinpoint areas to address.
3. Research salaries and benefits offered to teachers with similar experience levels in: comparable cities in the Philippines and other in-demand professions that might attract young, educated people away from teaching.
4. If major salary increases aren't feasible, explore non-monetary benefits that

improve the quality of life for teachers in far-flung schools: housing subsidies or assistance, transportation support, and childcare support (if relevant).

5. Develop ways to recognize teachers beyond performance ratings. Highlight those fostering a positive school climate, mentoring newer teachers, or going above and beyond for students.
6. Consider both formal awards and more informal, regular recognition to keep motivation high.
7. Provide time and structure for teachers to: plan lessons together, especially to address challenges in far-flung schools, share strategies for working with struggling students, and build a less isolating professional community, particularly in the remote areas. Survey teachers directly: what specific skills do they want to develop to address student difficulties? and what type of training formats are most accessible/beneficial to them?
8. If teachers desire graduate degrees and promotions, investigate: potential partnerships with universities to offer accessible courses (distance learning, weekend options, etc.) and clarify career advancement paths within the district and any barriers teachers might face in pursuing them.
9. Assess the potential for: more robust pre-K or early elementary programs to strengthen foundational skills early on and summer "bridge" programs for students before they enter grades where the skills gaps become major obstacles.
10. Use conclusions and recommendations as a starting point. Gather more data as you implement changes to measure their effectiveness.
11. Involve teachers in the design of solutions. This boosts buy-in and ensures programs will meet their needs.
12. While some recommendations might have general value, tailor them specifically to the budget limitations, cultural norms, and resources available in Samar.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The research adhered to strict ethical guidelines. This ensured respondents were fully informed through a written and verbal explanation of the study's purpose, including their right to withdraw at any time without justification. Additionally, robust measures were implemented to guarantee the confidentiality of all participant information.

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REFERENCES

- Abbas, S. A., Kusumawardani, Z. N., Suprayitno, N. F., & Jafar, N. (2023). Driving Factors of Motivation and Its Contribution to Enhance Performance. *Innovative: Journal Of Social Science Research*, 3(2), 7266-7280.
- Ahmed, I. (2011). Relationship between motivation and job satisfaction: a study of higher educational institutions. *Journal of Economics and Behavioral Studies*, 3(2), 94-100.
- Castor, Generos (2017). Job satisfaction among the administrative staff of the Negros Oriental State University. Unpublished Master' Thesis in Master in Public Administration, Foundation University, Dumaguete City.
- Comighud, S (2020). Motivational factors in Relation to Teachers' Performance. *IJRDO - Journal of Social Science and Humanities Research*
- Courus, G. (2014). What makes a master teacher? Embodying Visionary Leadership, Leading a Learning Community. Posted on April 24, 2010. Retrieved from

ecology of education.net/write/?p=2406.

- Futalan, E. A. (2013). Perceived Extent of job satisfaction of elementary school heads in relation to their level of school-based management (SBM) practices. Unpublished Doctoral Dissertation, Foundation University, Dumaguete City.
- Musa, J. (2014). Role of school leadership in motivating teachers: A case of Ilala Municipality, Dar Es Salaam (Doctoral dissertation, The Open University of Tanzania).
- Rasheed, M. I., Humayon, A. A., Awan, U., & Ahmed, A. U. D. (2016). Factors affecting teachers' motivation: An HRM challenge for public sector higher educational institutions of Pakistan (HEIs). *International Journal of Educational Management*, 30(1), 101-114.
- Robbins, S. P. & De Cenzo, D. A. (2012). *Fundamental of management*. Pearson Education Limited. Retrieved from www.alibris.com/Fundamentals-of-Management-Stephen-P-Robbins/book/7850748.
- Ucag, M., Gerodias, E., Medel, A. F., & Chua, J. (2024). Navigating Educational Frontiers: Unweaving the Challenges Faced by Teachers in Far-flung Schools on Negros Island. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 20(3), 323-330.
- Zulueta, F. M. 2015. *Management theories and practices*. Academic Publication ISBN 971-707-069-5.